

Citation

Wickramasinghe, V., & Perera, S. (2013). Effects of perceived organization support and authority in decision making on quality of conformance. Proceedings of 8th International Research Conference on Management and Finance, pp. 458-467, University of Colombo, Sri Lanka, December 13.

Effects of perceived organisation support and authority in decision making on quality of conformance

Abstract: This study investigated effects of perceived organisation support and authority in decision making on quality of conformance. In doing so, the study tested the moderating effect of perceived organisation support on the relationship between authority in decision making and quality of conformance. Two-hundred and fifty-five shop-floor employees employed full-time in ISO 9001:2000 certified manufacturing firms in which the quality management system is in operation for at least 1 year in Sri Lanka responded to the survey questionnaire. Hierarchical regression analysis was used to test the moderation hypothesis. It was found that authority in decision making significantly positively influence quality of conformance. Further, perceived organisation support positively moderates the relationship between authority in decision making and quality of conformance.

Keywords: authority in decision making, perceived organisation support, quality of conformance.

1. Introduction

With the transformation of the entire world into a boundary less global village echoing the new mantra of world class products and services, organisations strive to provide global customers with the highest quality products and services. Quality of product or service delivery has become the essence of an organisation's survival and competitiveness in the highly competitive global market (Garvin, 1987; Lakhali, 2009; Thomas, 2001). Most importantly, there has been a growing realization that continual improvements in quality are often necessary to achieve and sustain good financial and operational performance.

In the achievement of highest quality in products, especially in the manufacturing, involvement of shop-floor workers has become very important. Shop-floor workers are the key to assure that products meet required specifications and perform as anticipated during their daily operations. Hence, organizations must develop and realize the full potential of their workforce and maintain an environment conducive to full participation, personal and organizational growth (Rao et al, 1999).

However, the literature suggests that many quality efforts do not reach their full potential due to human related issues, such as the lack of teamwork and insufficient employee involvement (Sun et al., 2000). Therefore, it is important to give a greater consideration for human aspects in managing quality.

In the above context, this research investigated effects of perceived organisation support and authority in decision making on quality of conformance. Therefore, specific objectives of the study were to investigate 1) the relationship between authority in decision making and quality of conformance, and b) the moderating effect of perceived organisation support (POS) on the relationship between authority in decision making and quality of conformance.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Quality of Conformance

Quality management systems have been widely recognized as a fundamental business management strategy to strengthen the competitive position in local as well as global markets (Lakhali, 2009; Wickramasinghe & Wickramasinghe, 2012). The success of any quality management system depends on the measurable improvements in quality. In other words, the efforts of any quality improvement process should be reflected in improved quality levels based on objective measures derived from the analysis of product design through manufacture and delivery to the customer (Raghunathan et al., 1997; Rao et al, 1999; Thomas, 2001; Wanniarachchi et al., 2008).

Quality conscious customers all over the world demand to be assured that products or services they purchase meet required specifications and perform as anticipated. Quality of conformance refers to meeting products to pre-established physical and performance quality standards (Garvin 1984; Lindsay & Petrick 1997; Wickramasinghe, 2011). In other words, quality of conformance is the degree to which the design specifications are followed during the manufacture (Kontoghiorghes, & Gudgel, 2004). Therefore, greater the degree of conformance, higher the level of quality of conformance.

2.2. Authority in Decision Making

The total quality human resource management (TQHRM) is an approach to human resources management that involves many of the concepts of quality management (Thomas, 2001). The total quality human resource management environment is identified as providing employee empowerment through alignment, authority, capability and commitment. The full potential of employee empowerment could be realized in an empowered organization, when employees: align their goals with appropriate higher organization purpose; have the authority and opportunity to maximize their contribution; are capable of taking appropriate action; are committed to the organization's purpose; and have the means to achieve it (Dissanayake & Wickramasinghe, 2010).

Authority in decision making have been considered by job enrichment theorists (e.g., Herzberg, 1976) to provide an opportunity for self-actualization. The subject's perceptions of the opportunities having to make decisions, the time allowed for making these decisions, the control the job gives the subject over others and what goes on around him/her, and the authority he/she is delegated are considered as important in deciding authority in decision making (London & Klimoski, 1975; Wickramasinghe, 2013).

In the quality context, employees' job responsibilities expand to include a wider range of activities, such as planning, problem solving and quality assurance (Snell & Dean, 1994; Youndt et al., 1996). Therefore, the quality management literature emphasizes the importance of people involvement in quality processes and systems in a meaningful way to maintain the designed quality and to make continuous improvements in quality (Zink, 2008; Joiner, 2007; Bou & Beltrán, 2005; Wanniarachchi & Wickramasinghe, 2010). Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H1: Authority in decision making will positively influence quality of conformance

2.3. Perceived Organisation Support

Perceived organization support refers to employees' perception concerning the extent to which the organization values their contribution and cares about their well-being. Such POS would increase employees' felt obligation to help the organization reach its objectives, their affective commitment to the organization, and their expectation that improved performance would be rewarded. Therefore, in the situations of POS, employees believe that their increased effort towards achieving organisational goals will be noticed and rewarded (Eisenberger et al., 1997).

The literature identifies POS as an important determinant of quality performance, where POS plays a significant role in encouraging or impeding employees' effort toward reaching quality goals and employees' commitment to continuous improvement of processes (Montes et al., 2003; Hackman & Wageman, 1995; Joiner, 2007). Montes et al. (2003) suggest that employees' perception of tolerance, support, cohesion and the intrinsic acknowledgement of employees' organisational contributions are important aspects in the successful implementation of quality management systems. Further, Hackman and Wageman (1995) suggest that if quality management systems are implemented within a supportive organisation environment, employees will be more likely to work harder and smarter in achieving quality outcomes. Furthermore, Joiner (2007) empirically supported a positive significant relationship between POS and quality management system implementation. According to Joiner (2007), if employees do not feel there is acknowledgement and support from the organisation then the implementation of quality management systems may be sub-optimal. Hence, based on the findings, Joiner (2007) emphasized the importance of developing an environment of support to increase the performance outcomes of quality management systems. Therefore, it is hypothesised:

H2: Perceived organization support will moderate the relationship between authority in decision making and quality of conformance

Research model is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Research Model
Source: Author

3. Methodology

3.1. Sample

The target population for the study is a cross-section of shop-floor employees employed full-time in ISO 9001:2000 certified manufacturing firms in which a quality management system is in operation for at least 1 year in Sri Lanka. Twelve firms willingly participated in the survey. The contact person from each firm together with one of the authors of this article randomly selected shop-floor employees to be participated in this study. In doing so, attempts were made to select a cross-section of shop-floor employees from each firm. Further, participants were briefed about the aims of the study prior to the questionnaire distribution and their responses were anonymous. Four-hundred survey questionnaires were distributed among the firms covering at least 10% of the total shop-floor employees in each firm. Two-hundred and fifty-five usable responses resulted in a 64% response rate. The firms that responded belong to cable, gasket and solid tyre, radial tyre, polythene bags, electric accessories, school accessories, and floor tile manufacturing industries. The characteristics of the sample are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Sample characteristics

Age (in yrs):		
Mean		31
S.D.		8
Gender:		
Male		85%
Female		14%
Marital status:		
Single		58%
Married		41%
Highest level of education:		
Up to 10 years		63%
Up to 13 years		37%
Experience in present workplace (in yrs):		
Mean		8
S.D.		6
Number of employees in the present workplace:		
200 to 400		33%
More than 400		67%
Years of business existence:		
Mean		35
S.D.		12
The age of ISO certification		
5 to 10 years		60%
More than 10 years		40%

3.2. Measures

POS was measured using the Likert scale of Eisenberger et al., (1997, for the scale refer to Eisenberger et al. 1997). Factor analysis yielded one factor, where $\alpha = 0.873$, explained variation = 67.23%, and average variance extracted = .61. Authority in decision making was measured using the Likert scale of London and Klimoski (1975, for the scale refer to London and Klimoski, 1975). Factor analysis yielded one factor, where $\alpha = 0.721$, explained variation = 61.92%, and average variance extracted = .59. Quality of conformance was measured by the 3-item Likert scale developed for this study based on the literature reviewed earlier. The three items were “We ensure degree of conformity of our products with specifications”, “We ensure meeting pre-established physical and performance characteristics” and “We adheres to work instructions/guidelines when manufacturing products. Factor analysis yielded one factor, where $\alpha = 0.811$, explained variation = 69%, and average variance extracted = .66.

3.3. Methods of Data Collection and Analysis

A self-administered survey questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection. construct validity was established by using widely cited and thoroughly researched measures and by providing appropriate (a) reliability, (b) factor structure with loadings above 0.7, and (c) convergent validity with values of average variance extracted above 0.5. The anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension. Variance inflation

factors were calculated and those were between 1.20 and 2.78. Overall, the results of these tests revealed that multicollinearity and response bias were not issues in our data.

Hierarchical regression analysis was used to test the moderation hypothesis. The variables were entered into the regression equation in four steps. The control variables were entered in the first step, the independent variable was added in the second step, the moderator variable was added in the third step, and the interaction term was added in the fourth step. Following the recommendations of Aiken and West (1991), simple effects tests were conducted to determine whether the slopes differed significantly from zero.

4. Results and discussion

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics and correlations between variables. As can be seen in Table 2, authority in decision making is positively associated with quality of conformance. Similarly, POS is positively associated with quality of conformance. Further, authority in decision making and POS are positively associated.

Table 2 Correlations

	Mean	S.D.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1 Gender [†]	.85	.35	-									
2 Age [‡]	30.78	7.84	.300**	-								
3 Marital status [†]	.58	.49	.221**	.551**	-							
4 Experience [‡]	7.73	6.63	.174**	.813**	.411**	-						
5 Education [†]	.36	.48	-.147*	.280**	-.120	-.254**	-					
6 No. of Employees [‡]	.67	.46	-.286**	-.060	-.037	.028	.062	-				
7 ISO duration [‡]	.39	.49	.334**	.271**	.221**	.296**	-.087	.563*	-			
8 Business existence [‡]	35.06	11.95	.334**	.227**	.182**	.237**	-.145*	.623*	.641*	-		
9 Authority in decision making	3.76	.32	-.003	.104	.068	.099	-.037	.055	.123	.046		
10 POS	3.57	.68	.058	.073	.156*	-.030	-.113	.103	.221*	.130*	-.083	
11 Conformance	4.23	.56	.004	.004	.042	.031	.004	.062	.164*	.028	.444**	.350**

Note: [†] binary coded, [‡] continuous scale, ** significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), * significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Author

Table 3 shows the results of hierarchical regression analysis. Hierarchical regression analysis was conducted to test the moderator effect of POS. First, control variables were regressed on the outcome variable. The results are shown in Table 3 (Model 1). Second, the effect of authority in decision making on quality of conformance was analysed. As shown in Table 3 (Model 2), authority in decision making is significantly positively related to quality of conformance. This supports Hypothesis 1. As the third step, POS was entered into the model. As shown in Table 3 (Model 3), POS significantly impacts on quality of conformance. Finally, the interaction term was entered into the model to test the moderating effect. Hypothesis 2 predicted that the relationship between authority in decision making and quality of conformance would be moderated by POS. As indicated by the significant interaction term in Table 3 (Model 4), POS moderated the relationship between authority in decision making and quality of conformance. Following the recommendations of Aiken and West (1991), simple effects tests were conducted to determine whether the slopes differed significantly from zero. These tests revealed that the relationship between authority in decision making and quality of conformance is moderated for low levels of POS ($t = 2.217, p < .05$), medium levels of POS ($t = 2.554, p < .05$) and high levels of POS ($t = 2.562, p < .05$) and was significantly different from zero.

When comparing the results of the present study with the results of the previous studies conducted in this area, present study supports the findings of previous studies (such as Joiner, 2007) that showed positive effects of POS on quality management system implementation. And also supports the arguments made by previous researchers (such as Joiner, 2007, Montes et al., 2003, and Zink, 2008) on the importance of developing an environment of support to maintain the designed quality and to make continuous improvements in quality. The results of the present study presented evidence that higher the authority employees are provided with, a higher level of design specifications will be followed during the manufacture suggesting a greater degree of conformance; this relationship would be further enhanced if employees perceive a greater degree of support from the organisation.

We were unable to find previous studies that investigated this moderating relationship. Therefore, we identify our findings make a unique contribution to the literature.

Table 3 Results of hierarchical regression analysis

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
<i>Step 1: Controls:</i>				
Gender	-.124	-.139	-.045	-.050
Age	-.007	-.006	-.012	-.014
Marital status	.047	.048	-.020	-.017
Experience	.003	.003	.016	.017
Education	.005	-.001	.059	.041
Employees	-.096	-.102	-.053	-.048
ISO duration	.335**	.354**	.187	.176
Business existence	-.004	-.004	-.004	-.004
<i>Step 2: Independent:</i>				
Authority in decision making		-.076	-.033	-.500*
<i>Step 3: Moderator:</i>				
POS			.375***	.024
<i>Step 4: Interaction term:</i>				
Authority in decision making x POS				.132*
R ² (Adj.)	.011	.017	.197	.213
F change	1.367	1.477	7.222***	7.251***

Note: * p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001.

Source: Author

5. Conclusions and Implications

Although the importance of workforce for successful quality management is recognized, previous research provides little empirical evidence on the effects of the human dimension on quality performance. The present study empirically investigated effects of perceived organisation support and authority in decision making on quality of conformance. It was found that authority in decision making significantly positively predict quality of conformance. Further, authority in decision making and POS are positively associated. Furthermore, POS enhances/moderates the relationship between authority in decision making and quality of conformance.

The findings have several managerial implications. Employers face dynamic and ever increasing challenges in this economy. Employers face the challenges of maintaining productivity, profitability as well as keeping their workforce engaged and satisfied with their jobs.

Environmental pressures, rising costs, and the needs of the workforce have placed management in a complicated situation. The answer lies with creating a work environment that engage employees towards exceptional performance. The leaders of the organization have the responsibility for creating a high level of workplace support for employees. A motivating environment is one that gives workers a sense of pride in what they do. To show supervisors and managers how to build a more productive work environment, leaders must adopt strategies that enhance employees' contributions to quality performance.

Further, the findings of the study imply that organisations should take steps to fully engage employees physically, cognitively, and emotionally during role performances, which will in turn enhance quality performance. However, if employees do not feel there is sufficient acknowledgement and support from the organisation and if they are not engaged physically, cognitively, and emotionally during role performances, then as a consequence firms may not reap the optimal benefits.

Therefore, leaders involved in quality management should be able to cultivate the feelings of acknowledgement and support from the organisation for employees' contributions and fully engage them in role performance. Hence, managers may need special training to deepen their knowledge of the concepts such as participation in decision making and POS in the context of quality management.

6. References

- Aiken, L.S., & West, S.G. (1991). *Multiple Regression: Testing and Interpreting Interactions*. Sage, Thousand Oaks, CA.
- Bou, J.C., & Beltrán, I. (2005). Total quality management, high-commitment human resource strategy and firm performance: An empirical study. *Total Quality Management*, 16(1), 71–86.
- Dissanayake, D.M.M.M., & Wickramasinghe, V. (2010). A job satisfaction index to investigate the relationship between employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment. *Proceedings of International Conference on Business and Information*, University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka, June 4.
- Eisenberger, R., Cummings, J., Armeli, S., & Lynch, P. (1997). Perceived organizational support, discretionary treatment, and job satisfaction. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 82(5), 812–820.
- Garvin, D. (1984). What does product quality really mean? *Sloan Management Review*, 34–52.
- Garvin, D.A. (1987). Competing on the eight dimensions of quality. *Harvard Business Review*, 65, 202–209.
- Hackman, J., & Wageman, R. (1995). Total quality management: empirical, conceptual and practical issues. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 40, 309–342.
- Herzberg, F. (1976). *The managerial choice*. Dow Jones-Irwin, Homewood, IL.
- Joiner, T.A. (2007). Total quality management and performance: The role of organisation support and co-worker support. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 24(6), 617–627.
- Kontoghiorghes, C., & Gudgel, R., (2004). Investigating the association between productivity and quality performance in two manufacturing settings, *Quality Management Journal*, 11(2), 8–20.
- Lakhal, L. (2009). Impact of quality on competitive advantage and organisational performance. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 60, 637–645.
- Lindsay, W., & Petrick, J. (1997). *Total quality and organization development*. St. Lucie Press, Boca Raton.
- London, M., & Klimoski, R.J. (1975). A study of perceived job complexity. *Personnel Psychology*, 28, 45–56.
- Montes, F., Jover, A., & Fernandez, L. (2003). Factors affecting the relationship between total quality management and organisational performance. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 20(2), 189–209.
- Raghunathan, T.S., Rao, S.S., & Solis, L.E. (1997). A comparative study of quality practices: USA, China and India. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 97(5/6), 192–200.
- Rao, S.S., Raghunathan, T.S., & Solis, L.E. (1999). The best commonly followed practices in the human resource dimension of quality management in new industrializing countries: the case of China, India and Mexico. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 16(3), 215–225.
- Snell, S. A. & Dean, J. W. (1994). Strategic compensation for integrated manufacturing: the moderating effects of job and organisational inertia. *Academy of Management Journal*, 37, 1109–1140.
- Sun, H. Hui, I.K., Tam, A.Y.K., & Frick, J. (2000). Employee involvement and quality management. *The TQM Magazine*, 12(5), 350–354.
- Thomas, F.S. (2001). *Managing Quality: An Integrative Approach*. Prentice-Hall, New Jersey.
- Wanniarachchi, K.D.T., & Wickramasinghe V. (2010). Causes and mediating effect of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on absenteeism and labour turnover in the Sri Lankan export apparel manufacturing industry. *Proceedings of International Conference on Business Management 2010*, pp. 85–100, Sri Lanka, May 14. <https://journals.sjp.ac.lk/index.php/icbm/article/view/761>
- Wanniarachchi, T., Wickramasinghe V., & Wanigatunge, N. (2008). A comparative study on work-related attitudes of operational level employees and supervisors across firms of different ownership in Sri Lanka. *Proceedings of 14th Symposium of Engineering Research Unit*, pp. 120–121, University of Moratuwa, Sri Lanka, October 15. <http://dl.lib.mrt.ac.lk/handle/123/8172>
- Wickramasinghe, V. (2011). Influence of human dimensions on product quality. *Proceedings of 12th Annual Interdisciplinary Research Symposium of the Faculty of Graduate Studies, University of Kelaniya*. <http://repository.kln.ac.lk/handle/123456789/8127>
- Wickramasinghe, V. (2013). High performance work practices and performance of services outsourcing firms. *HRM Perspectives*, June, pp 1–18. <https://www.cipmlk.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/HRM-Perspectives-Final-2012.pdf>
- Wickramasinghe, V., & Wickramasinghe, G.L.D. (2012). Contribution of quality management practices on quality results. *Proceedings of Annual Academic Sessions*, pp. 175–178, The Open University of Sri Lanka, February 27–28. http://repository.ou.ac.lk/bitstream/handle/94ousl/796/OU5192_000.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y
- Youndt, M. A., Snell, S. A., Dean, J. W. & Lepak, D. P. (1996). Human resource management, manufacturing strategy, and firm performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 39, 836–866.
- Zink, K.J. (2008). Human resources and organisational excellence. *Total Quality Management*, 19(7–8), 793–805.